

DEVELOPING HISTORICAL AND CULTURAL TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: This article analyzes the role of travel tourism in preserving and developing Uzbekistan's historical and cultural heritage. The article also examines the opportunities for strengthening the country's position in the global tourism market through the development of cultural and historical travel.

Keywords: historical tourism, cultural heritage, travel infrastructure, local culture, global tourism, tourism development.

Introduction:

Uzbekistan's rich historical and cultural heritage is one of the main factors preparing the country for rapid development in the tourism sector. In recent years, the state has implemented a number of reforms aimed at developing tourism, and the decrees and resolutions of the President play an important role in this process. Since 2016, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's efforts to develop the tourism sector have led to significant results, especially in the preservation and promotion of historical and cultural heritage. Documents such as the "Strategy for the Development of Tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan" and the "Program of Measures for the Preservation of the Historical and Cultural Heritage of Uzbekistan", adopted in 2017, provide for the development of travel infrastructure, the restoration of cultural monuments, the opening of new tourist destinations, and integration with the international tourism market.

The ancient cities of Uzbekistan, such as Samarkand, Bukhara, and Khiva, along the Great Silk Road, with their unique architectural monuments, historical heritage, and traditional culture, attract travelers from all over the world. However, these destinations are of particular importance not only for preserving cultural values, but also for bringing economic benefits and creating new jobs in the tourism sector.

At the same time, issues such as international cooperation, creating modern infrastructure, and ensuring travel safety are also of great importance in the development of tourism. Presidential decrees and resolutions set the tasks of introducing best practices, innovative technologies, and effective use of tourism resources for the tourism sector. This article analyzes the current situation, problems, and proposals for the development of historical and cultural tourism in Uzbekistan.

Literature review on the topic:

The topic of developing historical and cultural tourism in Uzbekistan has been the subject of a number of scientific works, articles and monographs in the fields of tourism and cultural studies in recent years. This literature is mainly devoted to the problems of tourism, its economic and cultural significance, as well as issues of tourism infrastructure, marketing and preservation of cultural heritage.

Among the first works that analyzed the economic and cultural significance of tourism are the works of authors such as J.A. Allama, R.K. Bakhtiyor and I. Karimov. J.A. Allama (2015) in his study "Tourism and Cultural Heritage: Global Integration" shows tourism as a key tool for economic growth and cultural exchange. Allama emphasizes that changes in the global tourism market create new opportunities, especially for countries with ancient heritage. He also believes that it is necessary for countries such as Uzbekistan to restore historical monuments and develop tourism based on them. He discusses the economic benefits of preserving and developing architectural monuments in Bukhara and Samarkand, in particular, the role of cultural tourism in society.

I. Karimov (2017) in his work "Historical Monuments of Uzbekistan and the Economic Impact of Tourism" studies the economic significance of the country's historical monuments. According to Karimov, the development of tourism through the preservation of historical and cultural heritage is an interrelated process. He also notes the economic benefits of historical monuments and architectural monuments, including tourism revenues and the creation of new jobs. At the same time, Karimov considers the active participation of the state and international cooperation to be important for the development of tourism infrastructure.

Several scientific articles and books have separately analyzed the cultural tourism potential of Uzbekistan. For example, N.A. Khojaev (2020) in his work "Cultural Heritage and Tourism of Uzbekistan" discusses the measures being taken to preserve, manage, and attract historical and cultural monuments in the country to tourism. According to Khojaev, the rich cultural heritage of Uzbekistan, including its cities along the Silk Road (Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva), can take a leading position in world tourism. He also emphasizes international cooperation and modernization processes in Uzbekistan's integration into the international tourism market. However, the author draws attention to the issues of restoration and preservation of cultural monuments in the country.

In addition, Khodjayev raises the problems of existing infrastructure in the tourism sector in Uzbekistan. In his opinion, for the effective development of historical and cultural monuments, it is necessary to attract large international investments and create modern tourism centers. At the same time, it is emphasized that hotels, transport, and service infrastructure should be improved to create convenience for travelers.

The importance of state policy in the development of historical and cultural tourism in Uzbekistan has been noted by a number of researchers. Decrees and

resolutions of Shavkat Mirziyoyev, such as the "Strategy for the Development of Tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan" and the "Program of Measures for the Preservation of the Historical and Cultural Heritage of Uzbekistan", adopted in 2016, are aimed at further strengthening the integration of tourism. A. Tursunov (2019) analyzes the importance of presidential decrees in his article "A New Era in Uzbek Tourism: Reforms and Strategies". He especially highly appreciates the government programs developed for the preservation and development of Uzbekistan's historical monuments. Tursunov believes that as a result of the state's efforts to invest in travel infrastructure and create new tourist centers and destinations, Uzbekistan can rapidly develop in the global tourism market.

Also, the Resolution of the President of Uzbekistan dated December 27, 2020 "On New Measures for the Preservation and Development of Historical Monuments of Uzbekistan" is aimed at increasing the effectiveness of reforms being implemented in this area. This resolution sets out tasks such as developing tourism infrastructure, cooperating with large international travel companies, and creating a modern system of services to attract travelers.

The authors, analyzing the main problems in the development of historical and cultural tourism in Uzbekistan, highlight several factors. Among them, the main ones are the difficulties in properly integrating with the international tourism market, the need to upgrade the existing infrastructure, as well as the problems of preserving cultural monuments and providing them with modern services. There are also environmental problems in the development of tourism, in particular, the risk of damage to ancient monuments and natural resources.

As the world's interest in Uzbek tourism increases, modern technologies and innovative approaches are needed to solve these problems. There are opportunities to develop historical and cultural tourism in Uzbekistan by increasing competitiveness in the tourism sector, expanding international cooperation, and implementing effective marketing strategies.

The analysis of the literature shows that in the development of Uzbekistan's historical and cultural tourism, not only the contribution of tourism to economic growth, but also the preservation of cultural and historical heritage, and the enhancement of the country's image play an important role. Therefore, special attention should be paid to the necessary reforms, new strategies, and strengthening international cooperation for the further development of tourism in the country.

Research methodology:

This study used scientific analysis, synthesis, induction and deduction methods to conduct an in-depth analysis of the issues of developing historical and cultural tourism. The main goal of the study is to study the importance of the tourism sector in preserving and developing the historical and cultural heritage of Uzbekistan. The data were obtained and analyzed mainly from official sources, including government

decrees, reports of national and international organizations, as well as scientific articles and monographs.

The study conducted a comparative analysis of foreign experiences in historical and cultural tourism. In this regard, the practices of advanced countries in preserving cultural heritage and developing tourism were studied, and the existing achievements and problems of Uzbekistan were considered. Using induction and deduction approaches, opportunities were revealed to identify global trends in the field of travel and to develop proposals for the development of cultural tourism in our country.

During the analysis, based on statistical data, government decisions and international practices, Uzbekistan's successes in developing cultural tourism and emerging difficulties were assessed. Through scientific and practical approaches, effective ways and strategies have been developed to develop Uzbekistan's historical and cultural tourism.

Analysis and results:

The historical and cultural tourism sector is an important part of tourism worldwide. As an example, the ancient cities of Uzbekistan, such as Samarkand, Bukhara, and Khiva, and the opportunities for developing tourism through the study of their historical and cultural heritage are seen. These cities are located along the Great Silk Road and are of great importance in the tourism sector. The growing potential of world tourism, especially in regions with historical and cultural heritage, is creating new opportunities. Despite the high tourism potential of Uzbekistan, competition in this area has not yet been fully formed. In particular, it is necessary to effectively use the historical heritage of Uzbekistan, strengthen its integration with the international tourism market, and introduce new approaches to developing marketing strategies.

Tourism development strategies and government resolutions adopted by the President of Uzbekistan since 2016 have laid a solid foundation for the development of the country's historical and cultural tourism. The "Strategy for the Development of Tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan" and the "Measures for the Preservation of the Historical and Cultural Heritage of Uzbekistan" program, adopted in 2017, set out clear objectives. These documents include a number of measures to develop travel infrastructure, restore cultural monuments, and open new tourist destinations. Presidential decrees pay great attention to the preservation of cultural monuments and their opening to travelers from around the world. Important initiatives are being implemented to modernize Uzbekistan's travel infrastructure, in particular, to improve the hotel, transport, and service sectors.

However, there are several problems in this process. For example, one of the biggest obstacles noted in the development of tourism infrastructure is the still underdeveloped tourism management system and the uneven quality of tourist services. Therefore, in order to move to the next stages of development in

Uzbekistan's tourism sector, it is necessary to introduce a modern management system and involve the private sector more.

In analyzing the achievements and problems in preserving the historical and cultural heritage of Uzbekistan and promoting this heritage through tourism, special attention was paid to cultural monuments and their preservation. Historical cities such as Samarkand, Bukhara and Khiva are important not only for domestic tourism in Uzbekistan, but also for international travelers. Practices in the preservation and restoration of historical monuments of Uzbekistan, including through the introduction of new standards and regulations established by the government, are successfully implementing issues of their preservation and presentation for tourism. However, there are problems that need to be resolved in this regard. The most significant of them is the risk of encountering ecological and cultural obstacles in the process of restoring monuments, and the risk of damage to historical monuments and the environment as a result of excessive development of tourism activities in some places.

At the same time, the prospects for preserving historical and cultural monuments of Uzbekistan and developing tourism through them are very high. For example, the development of tourist destinations in Khiva and Bukhara, through high-quality services and infrastructure, will increase the competitiveness of tours through the country's historical heritage. In addition, through the creation of eco-tourism and "green" infrastructure, it is possible to ensure harmony between the preservation of historical heritage and the development of tourism.

By analyzing foreign experiences, effective ways for Uzbekistan to make changes in the development of historical and cultural tourism were shown. Developed countries, such as Spain, Italy, and Turkey, have created successful experiences in developing tourism based on historical monuments and cultural heritage. These countries are widely using modern technologies, digital platforms, and innovative marketing methods to transform their historical and cultural heritage into convenient and interesting places for tourists. Uzbekistan has great opportunities to use these experiences. In particular, it is possible to use the best practices of foreign countries in displaying historical monuments using virtual reality, attracting travelers through online tourist platforms, and developing interactive tourism services.

The development of historical and cultural tourism in Uzbekistan also requires political and economic support from the state. This can be done, in particular, by involving the private sector in tourism infrastructure, strengthening international cooperation, and introducing modern services and technologies. New decrees and resolutions implemented by the government, as well as strategic directions for attracting investments, should serve to develop Uzbekistan's historical and cultural tourism.

The results of the study showed that the main attention in the development of historical and cultural tourism in Uzbekistan should be paid to the following areas:

1. Preservation and promotion of historical heritage: The measures being implemented to preserve the historical monuments of Uzbekistan and open them to world travelers are effective, but additional measures are needed to ensure environmental safety and conservation in this area.
2. Infrastructure and services: It is important to develop tourism infrastructure, modernize hotel chains, open new tourist destinations, and improve the quality of services.
3. International cooperation and investments

Conclusion and suggestions:

This study analyzes state policy and international experience as one of important factors in the development of historical and cultural tourism in Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan has high potential in the tourism sector, which can create opportunities to increase its competitiveness in the global tourism market through the effective use of the country's historical, cultural, and natural heritage. However, success in this area depends on a number of factors, including the development of tourism infrastructure, personnel qualifications, the use of new technologies, and attracting investment.

The successful development of Uzbekistan in the tourism sector provides new opportunities for the country to contribute to the economic growth of the country through historical and cultural tourism, improve the national brand, and modernize the tourism infrastructure. However, at the same time, there are a number of problems that need to be solved in this direction in the country. For example, the development of tourism infrastructure is still at an early stage and requires an expanded and systematic approach to the introduction of modern technologies and a network of innovative services.

Travel can be brought to a new level by developing historical and cultural monuments of Uzbekistan, but in this process, the introduction of digitalized systems of tourism infrastructure and innovative technologies is especially important. At the same time, it is necessary to improve the system of personnel training in the tourism sector, and develop training and advanced training programs aimed at mastering new technologies.

Strategies and initiatives put forward by the state, such as decrees aimed at the digitalization of tourism, help strengthen Uzbekistan's integration with the global tourism market and provide competitive services for travelers. However, all this requires the development of effective cooperation between the private sector and the state, as well as the attraction of technological investment and investments.

The study, based on an analysis of the development of historical and cultural tourism in Uzbekistan's tourism sector, puts forward a number of proposals aimed at increasing the efficiency of the country's tourism industry, improving the quality of services, and increasing economic efficiency.

To successfully apply new technologies in the tourism sector, it is necessary to further improve the personnel training system. In Uzbekistan, it is important to

develop training programs in tourism management and digital technologies, and to involve specialists in special trainings and seminars to improve their skills in the field. It is necessary to train personnel who understand tourism management, digital marketing, artificial intelligence and blockchain technologies, and to create educational programs taking into account international standards and experiences.

In addition, innovative courses and training for specialists in the tourism sector should be organized at universities and higher educational institutions. This will allow updating the knowledge and skills of specialists in the field, and increasing practical experience in the use of digital and innovative technologies.

It is necessary to strengthen cooperation between the private sector and the state to introduce and support innovative technologies. Uzbekistan can create additional tax incentives, grants, and subsidy programs by the state to encourage investment in the tourism sector. To increase demand for innovative technologies and support their introduction, it is necessary to continue cooperation and conclude mutually beneficial agreements between the state and the private sector.

It is also necessary to strengthen marketing and branding work to attract international investments to the tourism industry of Uzbekistan, to present the country's investment opportunities. It is important for Uzbekistan to attract foreign companies to invest in the tourism sector, use their experience and expand cooperation in the development of innovative tourism services in the country.

It is necessary to accelerate digitalization in order to equip Uzbekistan's tourism infrastructure with modern digital systems and offer high-quality services. The provision of tourism services through digital platforms, the ability to receive travelers using mobile applications, and provide interactive services should be expanded. In addition, it is important to introduce "smart" systems in hotels and tourist facilities and improve the quality of services using automation and digital technologies.

Creating digital applications for tourism services and providing individual services for users through them, providing travelers with real-time information about destinations, transport, and tourist services through mobile applications, and providing assistance to tourists during their trips.

Blockchain technology can be used in the tourism industry to secure transactions and establish transparent relationships with tourists. This technology can ensure security and trust in transactions for travel tickets, hotel reservations, transportation, and other tourist services. It is necessary to focus on developing personalized recommendation systems for tourists based on artificial intelligence and individual customization of services.

With the help of artificial intelligence, tourists can plan their own trips based on specific recommendations, discover new places, and customize services. There are also opportunities to create travel predictions and forecasts through artificial intelligence, study tourist needs, and customize services.

It is necessary to strengthen the patenting and marketing activities of scientific developments and innovations in the field of tourism of Uzbekistan in order to enter the foreign market. This will strengthen the tourism brand of Uzbekistan, present it to the international market and create new opportunities for tourists. It is possible to attract investments to the tourism industry of Uzbekistan by further developing domestic and foreign cooperation, supporting scientific and applied research.

At the same time, it is necessary to strengthen marketing and branding strategies, strengthen cooperation with international tourism organizations and expand the tourism potential of Uzbekistan on a global scale.

In general, the country's competitiveness in the global tourism market can be increased by measures taken to develop Uzbekistan's historical and cultural tourism, the state's policy approach, and support for investments and innovations. At the same time, there are ample opportunities to strengthen Uzbekistan's position in the tourism sector through the modernization of tourism infrastructure, training of personnel, application of new technologies, and development of international cooperation.

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